

Empowering Women in Rural Tamil Nadu: Advancing Agricultural Workforce Transformation

Dr. Gopi Devarajan¹, Dr. Suganya Ilango², Dr. Stephy Christina S³, Dr. Ho Man Giang⁴, Dr. K. Malathi⁵

Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Faculty of Science and Humanities, SRM Institute of Science and Humanities, Kattankulathur, Chengalpattu-603203.¹

Assistant Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Science and Humanities, SRM Institute of Science and Humanities, Kattankulathur, Chengalpattu-603203.²

Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Faculty of Science and Humanities, SRM Institute of Science and Humanities, Kattankulathur, Chengalpattu-603203.³

HOD of Faculty of Business Administration - DONG A University, Vietnam.⁴

Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, University of Madras, Chepauk, Chennai-600 005.⁵

Abstract— The economy is undergoing structural transition, and Indian agriculture faces significant problems. The ongoing agrarian crisis is characterized by farmer suicides and the feminization of agriculture. It is not overstated to suggest that women are the stewards of food and nutritional security due to their various roles in agriculture and home activities. The workforce participation rate is an essential indicator of how the country's labour force is changing. The current study uses secondary data. The workforce engagement of men and women in rural India and Tamil Nadu was analyzed using census data collected over three decades from 1991 to 2011. National Sample Survey Organization data from several reports, as well as recent NSSO migration data (70th round), are analyzed to determine rural female outmigration in Tamil Nadu. The findings indicate that rural India and Tamil Nadu are experiencing a rise in workforce participation. Women's participation in the total workforce was higher in 2011 than in 2001 and 1991 in both India and Tamil Nadu. Simultaneously, the proportion of women working in agriculture in India and Tamil Nadu is decreasing. This indicates that more women have left agriculture over the decades. The investigation reveals evidence of feminization of agriculture and marginalization of agricultural laborers in Tamil Nadu.

Keywords- Agriculture, Feminization, Marginalization, Work force participation rate, Migration.

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture continues to be India's most important economic sector and a vital part of the country's overall socioeconomic structure. Over 60 percent of the workforce gets their food from agriculture in one form or another. The importance of having a robust agricultural industry cannot be overstated, as "food security" has come to serve as a global benchmark for policymakers. Nonetheless, there are difficulties with Indian agriculture. The country's economy is undergoing structural change, and between 1991 and 2001, the average number of farmers in the nation left the field. Suicides among farmers and the feminization of agriculture are signs of the agrarian crisis.

Indian women living in rural areas work in agriculture substantially. Their involvement is determined by socioeconomic status, cropping patterns, and agricultural production systems. Women work in agriculture in a variety of capacities, including managers, cultivators, and laborers. In India, women run the majority of farms, with their labor participation ranging from 55 to 66 percent on average. Women make up for 33 percent of cultivators and 47 percent of agricultural laborers in rural India (Vepa, 2005). They have contributed significantly to the growth of agriculture and related industries and still do. Achieving the intended general growth of the nation might not be feasible without the participation of women, both intellectually and physically.

II. STATE OF AGRICULTURE IN TAMIL NADU

The agricultural sector employs over 56 percent of the people in Tamil Nadu. Nearly 13 percent of the state's net domestic product comes from agriculture. There are 81.93 lakh land holdings in total, with small and marginal farmers owning roughly 91 percent of the total land. The total cultivated land is 55.72 hectares, with 58 percent of that area being used for irrigated agriculture. Compared to the 1195 mm average for all of India, the average annual rainfall in this region is 930 mm (Season and Crop Report, 2022).

The main crop of Tamil Nadu is rice, but it also grows sugarcane, cotton, and legumes. Women must work in agriculture because of the planting pattern and agricultural conditions. The majority of agricultural tasks are completed by women; they include planting, transplanting, weeding, and harvesting. Women's involvement in agriculture increases dramatically when they assume the position of de facto head of the home (Zing et al, 2006).

III. OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

The study aims to examine the main and marginal workforce participation rates of men and women by district as well as the proportion of women in Tamil Nadu who work as agricultural laborers and cultivators. This research makes use of secondary data from the 1991, 2001, and 2011 Indian Censuses. Data were gathered district-wise on the percentage of women who work as cultivators, agricultural laborers, primary workers, marginal workers, and job seekers. Additionally, the Department of Economics and Statistics provided district-specific data on the sex ratio, literacy rate, Gross District Domestic Product (GDDP), and the proportion of the primary sector in GDDP.

Compared to men, women have less access to productive resources. If they had the same access, their yield may have increased by 20 to 30 percent, increasing the total agricultural output in developing nations by 2.5 to 4 percent. Women in agriculture have not always been able to take advantage of opportunities presented by new technologies, expanding markets, and new forms of market access. Other negative factors that have affected them include migration from rural to urban areas, increasing pressure on land, water, and agricultural biodiversity, and natural disasters linked to climate change (ICAR, 2022).

According to Ghosh (2014), the ability of female labor to multitask has important implications for household food security, rural production, economic sustainability, agricultural output, and the health and welfare of families. Additionally, 75 million women work in the dairy industry compared to 15 million men, and 20 million women work in animal husbandry compared to 1.5 million men. The study's conclusion noted that, with a few exceptions like Kerala, Punjab, and West Bengal, where women actively engage in non-agricultural activities like the household industry, service sector, etc., women are involved in and participate in the agricultural sector in nearly all states.

As a result, the literature review highlights that employment is mostly provided by agriculture, especially for rural women. Women encounter numerous obstacles, such as limited time and mobility, in addition to disparities in pay. Male out-migration from low-paid agriculture to high-paid industries has resulted in a significant increase in the amount of work performed by women, notably in agriculture.

IV. DISCUSSION-I

PART I: ANALYSIS OF THE CENSUS DATA WORKFORCE

COMPOSITION IN INDIA AND TAMIL NADU

Both the rural and urban workforce compositions in Tamil Nadu and India have increased in 2011 as compared to 20 years earlier (Table 1). Tamil Nadu's Total Workforce Participation Rate (TWFP) was 44.67 in 2001 and 45.6 in 2011, which is 5 percent higher than the overall workforce participation rate of 39 percent in India. At roughly 51 percent, it remains high for Tamil Nadu's rural areas.

TABLE I
TOTAL WORKFORCE COMPOSITION OF INDIA AND TAMIL NADU (IN PERCENTAGE)

	1991	2001	2011
India (Total)	37.46	39.10	39.87
Rural	39.99	41.75	41.8
Urban	30.17	32.25	35.3
Tamil Nadu (Total)	43.31	44.67	45.6
Rural	48.49	50.28	50.7
Urban	33.34	37.54	40.2

Source: Census 1991, 2001 and 2011

SHARE OF WOMEN IN THE TOTAL WORKFORCE OF INDIA AND TAMIL NADU

The percentage of women in the labor force has increased in Tamil Nadu and throughout India, both in the rural and urban sectors (Table 2). With TWFPs for the overall, rural, and urban segments of 35 percent, 41 percent, and 25 percent, respectively, in 2001, Tamil Nadu's TWFP was higher than India in the same period. There are significant differences between 1991 and 2001. All things considered, the share of working women in Tamil Nadu is higher than the national average, it has been for the previous three decades. There were very modest changes between 2001 and 2011.

TABLE II
CLASSIFICATION OF WORK FORCE PARTICIPATION INDIA AND TAMIL NADU (RURAL AND URBAN)

	1991			2001			2011		
	TWFP	Male	Female	TWFP	Male	Female	TWFP	Male	Female
India (in millions)	314.13 (100.00)	224.36 (71.42)	89.76 (28.58)	402.23 (100.00)	275.01 (68.37)	127.22 (31.63)	481.74 (100.00)	331.86 (68.88)	149.87 (31.12)
Rural	249.02 (100.00)	168.59 (67.70)	80.43 (32.30)	309.95 (100.00)	198.83 (64.15)	111.11 (35.85)	348.59 (100.00)	226.76 (65.05)	121.83 (34.95)
Urban	65.10 (100.00)	55.76 (85.66)	9.33 (14.34)	92.27 (100.00)	76.17 (82.55)	16.10 (17.45)	133.14 (100.00)	105.10 (78.93)	28.04 (21.07)
Tamil Nadu (in lakhs)	241.94 (100.00)	159.57 (65.96)	82.36 (34.04)	278.78 (100.00)	181.00 (64.93)	97.77 (35.07)	328.84 (100.00)	214.34 (65.18)	114.49 (34.82)
Rural	178.34 (100.00)	108.21 (60.63)	70.12 (39.32)	175.59 (100.00)	103.60 (59.00)	71.99 (41.00)	188.61 (100.00)	112.14 (59.45)	76.46 (40.55)
Urban	63.60 (100.00)	51.36 (80.75)	12.24 (19.25)	103.18 (100.00)	77.39 (75.01)	25.78 (24.99)	140.23 (100.00)	102.20 (72.88)	38.02 (27.12)

Source: Census 1991, 2001 and 2011

INCREASE IN FEMALE MARGINAL WORKERS IN INDIA AND TAMIL NADU

The proportion of marginal workers in rural India's labor force grew from 10.74 percent in 1991 to 26.07 percent in 2001 and over 30 percent in 2011. Concurrently, throughout the course of three decades, the percentage of primary workers fell from 89.26 percent to 76.33 percent and 70 percent, respectively. According to absolute numbers, the number of workers in rural areas grew from 26 million in 1991 to 81 million in 2001 and finally to 103 million in 2011 (Table 3). It is considerably more horrible in Tamil Nadu's rural areas. From 7 percent in 1991 to 41 percent in 2001, the proportion of marginal workers rose and then fell to 18.6 percent in 2011. Between 1991 and 2001, the number of marginal workers rose from 12.56 lakhs to 71.99 lakhs. In 2011, it was cut in half to roughly 35 lakhs. The percentage of marginal workers in Tamil Nadu as a whole rose from 5.7 percent in 1991 to 35 percent in 2001 before falling to 15 percent in 2011.

FEMALE WORKERS IN RURAL TAMIL NADU: DISTRICT WISE ANALYSIS

TABLE III
DISTRICT WISE FEMALE WORKERS IN RURAL TAMIL NADU – (TOP AND BOTTOM 3 DISTRICTS)

	1991	2001	2011
Tamil Nadu (Rural)	35.13	36.77	37.72
Top three districts			
Virudhunagar	44.44	Tirunelveli	45.48
Tirunelveli Kattabomman	43.39	Perambalur	44.43
Chidambaranar	41.12	Virudhunagar	43.44
Bottom three districts			
Kanniyakumari	14.61	Kanchipuram	18.96
Thanjavur	28.35	Nagapattinam	27.79
Kanchipuram	31.45	Thiruvallur	27.98

Source: Census 1991, 2001 and 2011.

TABLE IV
DISTRICT WISE TOTAL MARGINAL FEMALE WORKERS IN RURAL TAMIL NADU – (TOP AND BOTTOM 3 DISTRICTS)

	1991	2001	2011
Tamil Nadu (Rural)	94.65	59.61	52.81
Top three districts			
Salem	96.96	Karur	67.50
Dharmapuri	96.90	Erode	66.76
Periyar	96.88	Perambalur	65.77
Bottom three districts			
Kanniyakumari	77.63	Kanniyakumari	35.69
The Nilgiris	82.17	Thiruvarur	48.16
Thanjavur	92.50	Nagapattinam	49.83

Source: Census 1991, 2001 and 2011.

The district wise total main and marginal rural female workforce for the top and bottom three districts are presented in the table 3 and 4. Though the districts are not strictly comparable because of bifurcation of districts in later 2000, the districts are only ranked to understand the participation of female in agriculture over three decades. Rural Tamil Nadu accounted for between 35 and 37 percent of all female main workers. Also, it can be inferred that Virudhunagar, Thirunelveli and Perambalur were the common districts there were among the top three over the three decades. At the same time, Kanniyakumari, Thiruvarur, Nagapattinam and

Kanchipuram were the bottom three districts repeatedly over the last three decades. In these districts, female rural workers were more than 40 per cent (Table 3).

Over the past three decades, Karur, Perambalur, Dharmapuri, and Salem have been among the top three districts in Tamil Nadu for the total number of female marginal laborers. In the meantime, for the previous three decades, Kanniyakumar, Thiruvarur, and Nagapattinam have consistently ranked among the lowest three districts. (Table No 4).

MAIN AND MARGINAL FEMALE CULTIVATORS IN RURAL TAMIL NADU

TABLE V
DISTRICT WISE TOTAL MAIN FEMALE CULTIVATORS IN RURAL TAMIL NADU – (TOP AND BOTTOM DISTRICTS)

	1991		2001		2011
Tamil Nadu (Rural)	26.02		34.71		35.43
Top three districts					
Kamarajar	37.15	Namakkal	44.69	Namakkal	46.74
Chidambaranar	32.32	Perambalur	43.54	Perambalur	44.76
Ramanathapuram	32.24	Ramanathapuram	42.78	Salem	42.66
Bottom three districts					
Kanniyakumari	5.93	Thiruvarur	15.95	Nagapattinam	15.32
Thanjavur	13.93	Nagapattinam	16.57	Thiruvarur	15.80
The Nilgiris	19.05	Kanniyakumari	19.33	Kanniyakumari	19.02

Source: Census 1991, 2001 and 2011.

TABLE VI
DISTRICT WISE TOTAL MARGINAL FEMALE CULTIVATORS IN RURAL TAMIL NADU – (TOP AND BOTTOM 3 DISTRICTS)

	1991		2001		2011
Tamil Nadu (Rural)	95.61		59.11		44.49
Top three districts					
Periyar	98.03	Erode	70.89	Namakkal	58.25
Dharmapuri	97.84	Salem	70.63	Coimbatore	55.42
Dindigul	97.36	Karur	69.63	Erode	54.69
Bottom three districts					
Kanniyakumari	83.58	Kanniyakumari	44.56	Nagapattinam	30.04
The Nilgiris	90.19	Thiruvarur	44.89	Thiruvarur	34.41
Tiruvannamalai	91.57	The Nilgiris	46.83	Tirunelveli	37.56

Source: Census 1991, 2001 and 2011.

The top and bottom three district wise details on the main and marginal female workers as cultivators in rural Tamil Nadu is presented in the table 5 and 6. Based on the figures, it can be deduced that while the percentage of women working as cultivators rose from 26 percent in 1991 to 35 percent in 2011, the percentage of marginal female workers as cultivators fell from 96 percent in 1991 to 44 percent in 2011. It can be noted that Namakkal, Perambalur and Ramanathapuram were among the top three districts in female main cultivators in all the three periods and Kanniyakumari, Thiruvarur and Nilgiris were among the bottom three for the same.

MAIN AND MARGINAL FEMALE AGRICULTURAL LABOURERS IN RURAL TAMIL NADU

TABLE VII
DISTRICT WISE TOTAL MAIN FEMALE AGRICULTURAL LABOURERS IN RURAL TAMIL NADU – (TOP AND BOTTOM 3 DISTRICTS)

	1991	2001	2011		
Tamil Nadu (Rural)	47.82	46.77	48.18		
Top three districts					
Thiruvannamalai	56.55	Perambalur	55.73	Namakkal	56.01
Ramanathapuram	54.71	Namakkal	54.70	Perambalur	55.90
Kamarajar	54.41	Karur	54.67	Karur	53.30
Bottom three districts					
Kanniyakumari	10.12	Nagapattinam	37.33	Kanniyakumari	20.49
Thanjavur	39.99	Thanjavur	38.74	Thiruvarur	38.37
The Nilgiris	41.70	Thiruvarur	38.77	Nagapattinam	39.15

Source: Census 1991, 2001 and 2011.

TABLE VIII
DISTRICT WISE TOTAL MARGINAL FEMALE AGRICULTURAL LABOURERS IN RURAL TAMILNADU – (TOP AND BOTTOM 3 DISTRICTS)

	1991	2001	2011		
Tamil Nadu (Rural)	95.53	62.55	57.23		
Top three districts					
Periyar	98.07	Karur	70.50	Salem	65.13
Salem	97.77	Namakkal	69.50	Karur	65.06
Dharmapuri	97.46	Ramanathapuram	69.31	Namakkal	63.76
Bottom three districts					
Kanniyakumari	79.10	Kanniyakumari	21.47	Kanniyakumari	27.90
Tiruvannamalai	92.22	Tirunelveli	51.57	Tirunelveli	48.53
The Nilgiris	92.43	Nagapattinam	53.14	Nagapattinam	50.72

Source: Census 1991, 2001 and 2011.

The top and bottom three district wise details on the main and marginal female workers as agricultural labourers in rural Tamil Nadu are presented in the table 7 and 8. Among all primary female workers, agricultural laborers in rural Tamil Nadu made up about 48 percent of the workforce. In 2001 and 2011, Perambalur, Namakkal, and Karur were in the top three. Kanniyakumari, Nagapattinam, Thanjavur and Thiruvarur were among the bottom three districts (Table 7). The share of female marginal workers a agricultural labourers decreased over the years from 95 per cent in 1991 to 57 per cent in 2011 (Table 8). Karur, Namakkal and Salem were among the top three districts and Kanniyakumari, Thirunelveli and Nagapattinam were the bottom three districts for the same.

IV. DISCUSSION-II

PART II : SELECT INDICATORS ON TOTAL RURAL FEMALES IN AGRICULTURE

The participation of rural female in agriculture may vary with so many factors. As paddy is the major crop in Tamil Nadu, area under paddy was taken for analysis. Area under sugarcane and cotton were also included study the participation of female workforce under cash crops. Studies have shown that the participation of rural females differs with irrigated and rainfed agriculture. Nearly 57 per cent of MNREGA beneficiaries are women in 2015-16, the highest ever

participation so far (The Hindu). As the programme was originally constituted to check migration and most of the MNREGA workers are women, the policy intervention variable was included. Other variables namely sex ratio, literacy rate, Gross District Domestic Product (GDDP), share of agriculture in GDDP were also included since they may influence the participation either positively or negatively.

$$Y_i = \alpha + \beta_1 X_{1i} + \beta_2 X_{2i} + \beta_3 X_{3i} + \beta_4 X_{4i} + \beta_5 X_{5i} + \beta_6 X_{6i} + \beta_7 X_{7i} + \beta_8 X_{8i} + \beta_9 X_{9i} + U_i$$

Where Y_i = Total Rural Female in Agriculture (**TRFA**)

X_{1i} = Sex ratio of females per 1000 males in 2011

X_{2i} = Literacy Rate for female as per 2011 Census

X_{3i} = GDDP (in Lakhs) in 2011

X_{4i} = Share of primary sector in GDDP (in Lakhs)

X_{5i} = Area under Sugarcane (Ha) in 2011.

X_{6i} = Area under Paddy (Ha) in 2011-12

X_{7i} = Area under Cotton (Ha) in 2011-12.

X_{8i} = Net area Irrigated (Ha) in 2011-12

X_{9i} = MGNREGA women beneficiaries in 2012.

R – 0.960

R² – 0.921

Adjusted R Square – 0.909

F-Statistics – 75.597

Independent Variables	Coefficient	t-statistics	p-value
Constant	356838.53	5.024	0.001*
Sex Ratio	-.065	-.192	0.703
Literacy Rate	-4370.44	-4.719	0.001*
GDDP	-.043	-.107	0.491
Share of Primary Sector in GDDP	-.086	-.251	0.683
Area under Sugarcane (Ha)	-.016	-.028	0.232
Area under Paddy (Ha)	-.353	-2.402	0.024**
Area under Cotton(Ha)	.063	.202	.810
Net Area Irrigated (Ha)	.731	3.747	0.001*
MGNREGA	.414	7.821	0.001*

* - 1 Per cent level of significance

** - 5 per cent level of significance

The results of the step-wise regression analysis indicate that the area under paddy is significant at the five percent level, whereas the literacy rate, net irrigated area, and MNREGA are significant at the one percent level. The involvement of rural females in agriculture declines as the literacy rate rises. Rural female engagement in agriculture rises with the net area under irrigation. The area covered by paddy has a negative coefficient; additional factors, such as mechanization, could be at play. It seems that, depending on what is available, rural women engage in MNREGA and agriculture in turn.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Over the years, more women have given up on agriculture, based on the analysis and overall findings. However, the proportion of female cultivators among all female primary workers has grown. Additionally, the proportion of female marginal agricultural laborers among all marginal workers is rising. There are indications of the marginalization of women in the workforce and the feminization of agriculture.

Therefore, in order to alleviate the issues experienced by rural women, both governmental and non-governmental organizations should comprehend and support their involvement in agriculture. Making agriculture viable and treating it like an industry are essential priorities. Instead of operating alone, agricultural, rural development, and migration policies ought to collaborate. Enhancing one's skills, getting access to resources, getting credit, and getting into the market are just a few of the numerous needs as, as the workforce in agriculture declines, so does the innate skill set that has been passed down through the generations.

REFERENCES

1. Behera, B. S., & Behera, A. C. (2013). Gender issues: The role of women in agriculture sector in India. *International Journal of Marketing, Financial Services & Management Research*, 2(9), 134-145.
2. Bhadra, C. (2007). International labor migration of Nepalese women: Impact of their remittances on poverty reduction.
3. Datta, A., & Mishra, S. K. (2011). Glimpses of women's lives in rural Bihar: Impact of male migration. *The Indian journal of labour economics*, 54(3), 457-477.
4. Gartaula, H. N., Niehof, A., & Visser, L. (2010). Feminisation of Agriculture as an Effect of Male Out-migration: Unexpected Outcomes from Jhapa District, Eastern Nepal. *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Social Sciences*, 5(2).
5. Ghosh, M., & Ghosh, A. (2014). Analysis of women participation in Indian agriculture. *IOSR J. Human. Soc. Sci*, 19(5), 1-6.
6. Govind Kelkar, G. K. (2007). The feminization of agriculture in Asia: implications for women's agency and productivity.
7. Goswami, C. (2013). Female agricultural workers in Assam: A case study of Darrang District. *International journal of scientific and research publications*, 3(2), 1-5.
8. Goswami, N., & Bordoloi, A. K. (2013). Female participation in agriculture: A literature review. *International Journal of Basic Applied & Social Sciences*, 1(1), 1-6.
9. Kumar, J. (2015). BIG DATA FOR SUBSIDY MECHANISM. *Scholedge International Journal of Business Policy & Governance*, 2(8).
10. Lobao, L., & Meyer, K. (2001). The great agricultural transition: crisis, change, and social consequences of twentieth century US farming. *Annual review of sociology*, 27(1), 103-124.
11. Mathew, S. S. (2012). Distress-driven employment and feminisation of work in Kasargod district, Kerala. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 65-73.
12. Patel, A. (2012). Empowering women in agriculture. *Yojana*, 56, 19-22.
13. Schuller, Oliver De (2013), "The Agrarian Transition and the Feminisation of Agriculture", Conference paper No. 37, Yale University, September 14- 15.
14. Season and Crop Report (2022), Department of Economics and Statistics, Tamil Nadu.
15. Tamang, S., Paudel, K. P., & Shrestha, K. K. (2014). Feminization of agriculture and its implications for food security in rural Nepal. *Journal of Forest and Livelihood*, 12(1), 20-32.
16. Thomas, J. J. (2016). Locked in a low-skill equilibrium? Trends in labour supply and demand in India (No. id: 10887).
17. Thomas, J. J. (2015). India's labour market during the 2000s. *Labour, employment and economic growth in India*, 21-56.
18. Vepa, S. S. (2005). Feminisation of agriculture and marginalisation of their economic stake. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 2563-2568. S. M. Metev and V. P. Veiko, *Laser Assisted Microtechnology*, 2nd ed., R. M. Osgood, Jr., Ed. Berlin, Germany: Springer-Verlag, 1998.